

Hyers-Ulam Stability of Functional Equation

$$f(3x) = 4f(3x - 3) + f(3x - 6)$$

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Abstract—The functional equation $f(3x) = 4f(3x - 3) + f(3x - 6)$ will be solved and its Hyers-Ulam stability will be also investigated in the class of functions $f : \mathbf{R} \rightarrow X$, where X is a real Banach space.

Keywords—Functional equation, Lucas sequence of the first kind, Hyers-Ulam stability.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN 1940, Ulam gave a wide ranging talk before the Mathematics Club of the University of Wisconsin in which he discussed a number of important unsolved problems (ref. [20]). Among those was the question concerning the stability of homomorphisms:

Let G_1 be a group and let G_2 be a metric group with a metric $d(\cdot, \cdot)$. Given any $\varepsilon > 0$, does there exist a $\delta > 0$ such that if a function $h : G_1 \rightarrow G_2$ satisfies the inequality $d(h(xy), h(x)h(y)) < \delta$ for all $x, y \in G_1$, then there exists a homomorphism $H : G_1 \rightarrow G_2$ with $d(h(x), H(x)) < \varepsilon$ for all $x \in G_1$?

In the following year, Hyers affirmatively answered in his paper [8] the question of Ulam for the case where G_1 and G_2 are Banach spaces. Later, the result of Hyers has been generalized by Rassias (ref. [16]).

Let (G_1, \cdot) be a groupoid and let $(G_2, +)$ be a groupoid with the metric d . The equation of homomorphism

$$f(x \cdot y) = f(x) + f(y)$$

is stable in the Hyers-Ulam sense (or has the Hyers-Ulam stability) if for every $\delta > 0$ there exists an $\varepsilon > 0$ such that for every function $h : G_1 \rightarrow G_2$ satisfying

$$d[h(x \cdot y), h(x) + h(y)] \leq \varepsilon$$

for all $x, y \in G_1$ there exists a solution $g : G_1 \rightarrow G_2$ of the equation of homomorphism with

$$d[h(x), g(x)] \leq \delta$$

for any $x \in G_1$ (see [15, Definition 1]).

This terminology is also applied to the case of other functional equations. It should be remarked that a lot of references concerning the stability of functional equations can be found in the books [3], [9], [12] (see also [1], [4], [5], [6], [7], [10], [11], [17], [18], [19]).

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The n th Fibonacci number will be denoted by F_n for $n \in \mathbf{N}$. It is well known that the Fibonacci numbers satisfy the equality $F_{3n} = 4F_{3n-3} + F_{3n-6}$ for all $n \geq 2$ (see [14, p. 89]). From this famous formula, the following functional equation

$$f(3x) = 4f(3x - 3) + f(3x - 6) \quad (1)$$

may be derived.

In this paper, using the idea from [13], the functional equation (1) will be solved and its Hyers-Ulam stability will be investigated in the class of functions $f : \mathbf{R} \rightarrow X$, where X is a real Banach space.

Throughout this paper, the positive and the negative root of the equation $x^2 - 4x - 1 = 0$ will be denoted by a and b , respectively, i.e.,

$$a = 2 + \sqrt{5} \quad \text{and} \quad b = 2 - \sqrt{5}.$$

Moreover, the Lucas sequence of the first kind will be denoted by $\{U_n(4, -1)\}$ and an abbreviation U_n will be used instead of $U_n(4, -1)$, i.e., U_n is defined by

$$U_n = U_n(4, -1) = \frac{a^n - b^n}{a - b}$$

for all integers n . It is not difficult to see that

$$U_{n+2} = 4U_{n+1} + U_n \quad (2)$$

for any integer n . For any $x \in \mathbf{R}$, $[x]$ stands for the largest integer that does not exceed x .

II. GENERAL SOLUTION TO EQ. (1)

Throughout this section, let X be a real vector space. The general solution of the functional equation (1) will be investigated.

Theorem 2.1. *Let X be a real vector space. A function $f : \mathbf{R} \rightarrow X$ is a solution of the functional equation (1) if and only if there exists a function $h : [-3, 3] \rightarrow X$ such that*

$$f(x) = U_{[x/3]+1}h(x - 3[x/3]) + U_{[x/3]}h(x - 3[x/3] - 3). \quad (3)$$

Proof. Since $a + b = 4$ and $ab = -1$, it follows from (1) that

$$\begin{cases} f(3x) - af(3x - 3) = b[f(3x - 3) - af(3x - 6)], \\ f(3x) - bf(3x - 3) = a[f(3x - 3) - bf(3x - 6)]. \end{cases}$$

If a function $g : \mathbf{R} \rightarrow X$ is defined by $g(x) = f(3x)$ for each $x \in \mathbf{R}$, then it follows from the above equalities that

$$\begin{cases} g(x) - ag(x-1) = b[g(x-1) - ag(x-2)], \\ g(x) - bg(x-1) = a[g(x-1) - bg(x-2)]. \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

By the mathematical induction, it can be proved that

$$\begin{cases} g(x) - ag(x-1) \\ = b^n [g(x-n) - ag(x-n-1)], \\ g(x) - bg(x-1) \\ = a^n [g(x-n) - bg(x-n-1)] \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{R}$ and $n \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$. Substitute $x+n$ ($n \geq 0$) for x in (5) and divide the resulting equations by b^n resp. a^n , and then substitute $-m$ for n in the resulting equations to obtain the equations in (5) with m in place of n , where $m \in \{0, -1, -2, \dots\}$. Therefore, the equations in (5) are true for all $x \in \mathbf{R}$ and $n \in \mathbf{Z}$.

Multiply the first and the second equation of (5) by b and a , respectively. And subtract the first resulting equation from the second one to obtain

$$g(x) = U_{n+1}g(x-n) + U_n g(x-n-1) \quad (6)$$

for any $x \in \mathbf{R}$ and $n \in \mathbf{Z}$.

Putting $n = [x]$ in (6) yields

$$g(x) = U_{[x]+1}g(x-[x]) + U_{[x]}g(x-[x]-1),$$

i.e., by the definition of g , it holds that

$$f(x) = U_{[x/3]+1}f(x-3[x/3]) + U_{[x/3]}f(x-3[x/3]-3)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{R}$.

Since $0 \leq x-3[x/3] < 3$ and $-3 \leq x-3[x/3]-3 < 0$, if a function $h : [-3, 3) \rightarrow X$ is defined by $h := f|_{[-3, 3)}$, then f is a function of the form (3).

Now, assume that f is a function of the form (3), where $h : [-3, 3) \rightarrow X$ is an arbitrary function. Then, it follows from (3) that

$$f(3x) = U_{[x]+1}h(3x-3[x]) + U_{[x]}h(3x-3[x]-3),$$

$$f(3x-3) = U_{[x]}h(3x-3[x]) + U_{[x]-1}h(3x-3[x]-3),$$

$$f(3x-6) = U_{[x]-1}h(3x-3[x]) + U_{[x]-2}h(3x-3[x]-3)$$

for any $x \in \mathbf{R}$. Thus, by (2), it holds that

$$\begin{aligned} f(3x) - 4f(3x-3) - f(3x-6) \\ = (U_{[x]+1} - 4U_{[x]} - U_{[x]-1})h(3x-3[x]) \\ + (U_{[x]} - 4U_{[x]-1} - U_{[x]-2})h(3x-3[x]-3) \\ = 0, \end{aligned}$$

which completes the proof.

III. HYERS-ULAM STABILITY OF EQ. (1)

In this section, a denotes the positive root of the equation $x^2 - 4x - 1 = 0$ and b is its negative root. The Hyers-Ulam stability of the functional equation (1) will be proved in the following theorem.

Theorem 3.1. Let $(X, \|\cdot\|)$ be a real Banach space. If a function $f : \mathbf{R} \rightarrow X$ satisfies the inequality

$$\|f(3x) - 4f(3x-3) - f(3x-6)\| \leq \varepsilon \quad (7)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{R}$ and for some $\varepsilon \geq 0$, then there exists a unique solution function $F : \mathbf{R} \rightarrow X$ of (1) such that

$$\|f(x) - F(x)\| \leq \frac{5 + \sqrt{5}}{20} \varepsilon \quad (8)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{R}$.

Proof. First, define a function $g : \mathbf{R} \rightarrow X$ by $g(x) = f(3x)$ for all $x \in \mathbf{R}$. Analogously to the first equation of (4), it follows from (7) that

$$\|g(x) - ag(x-1) - b[g(x-1) - ag(x-2)]\| \leq \varepsilon$$

for each $x \in \mathbf{R}$. Replacing x with $x-k$ in the last inequality yields

$$\begin{aligned} \|g(x-k) - ag(x-k-1) \\ - b[g(x-k-1) - ag(x-k-2)]\| \\ \leq \varepsilon \end{aligned}$$

and further

$$\begin{aligned} \|b^k [g(x-k) - ag(x-k-1)] \\ - b^{k+1} [g(x-k-1) - ag(x-k-2)]\| \\ \leq |b|^k \varepsilon \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{R}$ and $k \in \mathbf{Z}$. By (9), it obviously holds that

$$\begin{aligned} \|g(x) - ag(x-1) - b^n [g(x-n) - ag(x-n-1)]\| \\ \leq \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \|b^k [g(x-k) - ag(x-k-1)] \\ - b^{k+1} [g(x-k-1) - ag(x-k-2)]\| \\ \leq \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} |b|^k \varepsilon \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

for $x \in \mathbf{R}$ and $n \in \mathbf{N}$.

For any $x \in \mathbf{R}$, (9) implies that the sequence $\{b^n [g(x-n) - ag(x-n-1)]\}$ is a Cauchy sequence. (Note that $|b| < 1$). Therefore, a function $G_1 : \mathbf{R} \rightarrow X$ can be defined by

$$G_1(x) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} b^n [g(x-n) - ag(x-n-1)],$$

since X is complete. It follows from the definition of G_1 that

$$\begin{aligned} & 4G_1(x-1) + G_1(x-2) \\ &= 4b^{-1} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} b^{n+1} [g(x-(n+1)) \\ &\quad - ag(x-(n+1)-1)] \\ &\quad + b^{-2} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} b^{n+2} [g(x-(n+2)) \\ &\quad - ag(x-(n+2)-1)] \quad (11) \\ &= 4b^{-1}G_1(x) + b^{-2}G_1(x) \\ &= G_1(x) \end{aligned}$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{R}$, since $b^2 = 4b + 1$. If n goes to infinity, then (10) yields that

$$\|g(x) - ag(x-1) - G_1(x)\| \leq \frac{3 + \sqrt{5}}{4} \varepsilon \quad (12)$$

for every $x \in \mathbf{R}$.

On the other hand, it also follows from (7) that

$$\|g(x) - bg(x-1) - a[g(x-1) - bg(x-2)]\| \leq \varepsilon$$

(see the second equation in (4)). Analogously to (9), replacing x by $x+k$ in the above inequality and then dividing by a^k both sides of the resulting inequality yield

$$\begin{aligned} & \|a^{-k}[g(x+k) - bg(x+k-1)] \\ & \quad - a^{-k+1}[g(x+k-1) - bg(x+k-2)]\| \quad (13) \\ & \leq a^{-k} \varepsilon \end{aligned}$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{R}$ and $k \in \mathbf{Z}$. It further follows from (13) that

$$\begin{aligned} & \|a^{-n}[g(x+n) - bg(x+n-1)] - [g(x) - bg(x-1)]\| \\ & \leq \sum_{k=1}^n \|a^{-k}[g(x+k) - bg(x+k-1)] \\ & \quad - a^{-k+1}[g(x+k-1) - bg(x+k-2)]\| \quad (14) \\ & \leq \sum_{k=1}^n a^{-k} \varepsilon \end{aligned}$$

for $x \in \mathbf{R}$ and $n \in \mathbf{N}$.

On account of (13), the sequence $\{a^{-n}[g(x+n) - bg(x+n-1)]\}$ is a Cauchy sequence for any fixed $x \in \mathbf{R}$. Hence, a function $G_2 : \mathbf{R} \rightarrow X$ can be defined by

$$G_2(x) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} a^{-n}[g(x+n) - bg(x+n-1)].$$

It follows from the definition of G_2 that

$$\begin{aligned} & 4G_2(x-1) + G_2(x-2) \\ &= 4a^{-1} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} a^{-(n-1)} [g(x+n-1) \\ & \quad - bg(x+(n-1)-1)] \\ & \quad + a^{-2} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} a^{-(n-2)} [g(x+n-2) \\ & \quad - bg(x+(n-2)-1)] \quad (15) \\ &= 4a^{-1}G_2(x) + a^{-2}G_2(x) \\ &= G_2(x) \end{aligned}$$

for any $x \in \mathbf{R}$. By letting n go to infinity, (14) yields

$$\|G_2(x) - g(x) + bg(x-1)\| \leq \frac{\sqrt{5}-1}{4} \varepsilon \quad (16)$$

for $x \in \mathbf{R}$.

From (12) and (16), it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| g(x) - \left[\frac{b}{b-a}G_1(x) - \frac{a}{b-a}G_2(x) \right] \right\| \\ &= \frac{1}{|b-a|} \|(b-a)g(x) - [bG_1(x) - aG_2(x)]\| \\ &\leq \frac{1}{a-b} \|bg(x) - abg(x-1) - bG_1(x)\| \quad (17) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{a-b} \|aG_2(x) - ag(x) + abg(x-1)\| \\ &\leq \frac{5 + \sqrt{5}}{20} \varepsilon \end{aligned}$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{R}$. Now define a function $F : \mathbf{R} \rightarrow X$ by

$$F(x) = \frac{b}{b-a}G_1\left(\frac{x}{3}\right) - \frac{a}{b-a}G_2\left(\frac{x}{3}\right)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{R}$. Then, it follows from (11) and (15) that

$$\begin{aligned} & 4F(3x-3) + F(3x-6) \\ &= \frac{4b}{b-a}G_1(x-1) - \frac{4a}{b-a}G_2(x-1) \\ &\quad + \frac{b}{b-a}G_1(x-2) - \frac{a}{b-a}G_2(x-2) \\ &= \frac{b}{b-a}[4G_1(x-1) + G_1(x-2)] \\ &\quad - \frac{a}{b-a}[4G_2(x-1) + G_2(x-2)] \\ &= \frac{b}{b-a}G_1(x) - \frac{a}{b-a}G_2(x) \\ &= F(3x) \end{aligned}$$

for each $x \in \mathbf{R}$, i.e., F is a solution of (1). Moreover, the inequality (8) follows from (17).

The uniqueness of F will be proved. Assume that $F_1, F_2 : \mathbf{R} \rightarrow X$ are solutions of (1) and that there exist positive constants C_1 and C_2 with

$$\|f(x) - F_1(x)\| \leq C_1 \quad \text{and} \quad \|f(x) - F_2(x)\| \leq C_2 \quad (18)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{R}$. According to Theorem 2.1, there exist functions $h_1, h_2 : [-3, 3] \rightarrow X$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} F_1(x) &= U_{[x/3]+1}h_1(x-3[x/3]) \\ &\quad + U_{[x/3]}h_1(x-3[x/3]-3), \\ F_2(x) &= U_{[x/3]+1}h_2(x-3[x/3]) \\ &\quad + U_{[x/3]}h_2(x-3[x/3]-3) \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

for any $x \in \mathbf{R}$, since F_1 and F_2 are solutions of (1).

Fix a t with $0 \leq t < 3$. It then follows from (18) and (19) that

$$\begin{aligned} & \|U_{n+1}[h_1(t) - h_2(t)] + U_n[h_1(t-3) - h_2(t-3)]\| \\ &= \|[U_{n+1}h_1(t) + U_n h_1(t-3)] \\ &\quad - [U_{n+1}h_2(t) + U_n h_2(t-3)]\| \\ &= \|F_1(3n+t) - F_2(3n+t)\| \\ &\leq \|F_1(3n+t) - f(3n+t)\| + \|f(3n+t) - F_2(3n+t)\| \\ &\leq C_1 + C_2 \end{aligned}$$

for each $n \in \mathbf{Z}$, i.e.,

$$\left\| \frac{a^{n+1} - b^{n+1}}{a - b} [h_1(t) - h_2(t)] + \frac{a^n - b^n}{a - b} [h_1(t - 3) - h_2(t - 3)] \right\| \leq C_1 + C_2 \quad (20)$$

for every $n \in \mathbf{Z}$. Dividing both sides by a^n yields that

$$\left\| \frac{a - (b/a)^n b}{a - b} [h_1(t) - h_2(t)] + \frac{1 - (b/a)^n}{a - b} [h_1(t - 3) - h_2(t - 3)] \right\| \leq \frac{C_1 + C_2}{a^n}.$$

Let $n \rightarrow \infty$ to get

$$a[h_1(t) - h_2(t)] + [h_1(t - 3) - h_2(t - 3)] = 0. \quad (21)$$

Analogously, divide both sides of (20) by $|b|^n$ and let $n \rightarrow -\infty$ to get

$$b[h_1(t) - h_2(t)] + [h_1(t - 3) - h_2(t - 3)] = 0. \quad (22)$$

From (21) and (22), it follows that

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & 1 \\ b & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} h_1(t) - h_2(t) \\ h_1(t - 3) - h_2(t - 3) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Because $a - b \neq 0$, it should hold that

$$h_1(t) - h_2(t) = h_1(t - 3) - h_2(t - 3) = 0$$

for any $t \in [0, 3)$, i.e., $h_1(t) = h_2(t)$ for all $t \in [-3, 3)$. Therefore, it is true that $F_1(x) = F_2(x)$ for any $x \in \mathbf{R}$.

Remark 1. The presented proof of uniqueness of F is due to an idea of Professor Changsun Choi. It should be remarked that the uniqueness of F can be obtained directly from [2, Proposition 1].

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